

Figure S5. Transformation, ligation and restriction digestion analysis.

An *E. coli* DH5-alpha transformants carrying the synthetic SCMVCpaj405-pUC57-amp (a), and SCMVCpaj405-pET28 (a⁺) gene after shifting (b) using *Nde*I+ *Hind*III; C1, C2, C3, and C4 = colony numbers, and M = 1kb DNA ladder. SCMVCpaj405 (\pm 948 bp), pUC57-amp (~2710bp), and pET28 (a⁺) (~5369bp).

Figure S6. 6XHis-SCMVCpaj405 recombinantly expressed protein subcellular localization in *E. coli* BL21C+; (a) lane 1-2: total proteins extracted from *E. coli* with SCMVCpaj405-pET28 (a⁺) (induced and un-induced), lane 3: control plasmid only (induced); (b) lane 1-2 = soluble fractions, and pellet; M = unstained protein marker.

Figure S7. Optimization of indirect ELISA test for the detection of SCMV. (a) Polyclonal antibodies titer check in all experimental animals (C1, C2, and C3) immunized with 6XHis-SCMVCpaj405 purified protein compare with buffer and negative control (immunized with 1XPBS buffer); (b) optimization of primary antibody (serum) coating conc using serial dilution method; (c) Standard Curve plotted for optimization of antigen (6XHis-SCMVCpaj405 protein) coating conc by serial dilution method, and (d) linear regression shows a working range from 100 pg/ml to 1 µg/mL ($r^2 = 0.957$).

Table S1

Predicted antigenic epitopes of SCMVCpaj405 fusion protein by GenScript “OptimumAntigen Design Tool”.

No	Start	Antigenic Determinant	Length	Antigenicity/Surface/Hydrophilicity	Disordered Score	Synthesis	Mus_musculus blast
1	76	ETGSVTGGQRDKDVC	14	3.02/0.93/0.78	0.1466	Easy	49%

2	293	CNVGETQENTERHTA	14	2.78/0.86/0.78	0.1161	Easy	57%
3	105	MSKKMRLPKAKGKDC	14	2.61/0.71/0.96	0.1332	Easy	50%
4	130	CPQQQDISNTRATRE	14	1.84/0.86/0.67	0.1675	Easy	42%
5	259	CEMNSRTPARAKEAH	14	1.59/0.86/0.63	NONE	Easy	70%
6	228	CYRNSTERYMPRYGL	14	1.41/0.50/0.34	NONE	Easy	50%
7	191	CDGDEQRVFPLKPMI	14	1.19/0.57/0.42	NONE	Normal	70%
8	153	CKKEYEIDD ^T QMTVV	14	1.19/0.57/0.47	0.1015	Normal	49%

Warn:peptide--> PQQQDISNTRATRE :130 has no net charge, which may lead to dissolubility issues!

Warn:peptide--> YRNSTERYMPRYGL :228 consist of the candidate glycosylation sites!

Note:

1. An extra "C" (high-lighted as green) is added to the C-terminus (or N-terminus) to facilitate conjugation.
2. Positive charged residues (K,R,H) are in blue.
Negative charged residues (D,E) are in red.
3. Disorder peptide note: The linear conformation of a disordered peptide is more similar to its natural conformation in folded protein.

Table S2

Predicted subcellular localization site of SCMVCpaj405 native and fusion proteins by SOSUI_{GramN}.

ID	seg.Length	Subcellular Localization site
Native SCMVCpaj405 protein	314a.a.	P (Periplasm)
SCMVCpaj405 fusion protein	334a.a.	P (Periplasm)

Table S3.

Signal peptide score summary of SCMVCpaj405 predicted by SignalP-5.0 for Gram-negative bacteria.

# ID	Prediction	SP(Sec/SPI)	TAT(Tat/SPI)	LIPO(Sec/SPII)	OTHER	CS Position
Native SCMVCpaj405 protein	OTHER	0.296653	0.169714	0.054106	0.479527	OTHER
SCMVCpaj405 fusion protein	OTHER	0.218500	0.265910	0.023382	0.492208	OTHER